

Theoretical and Philosophical Article

The Problems of Necessity and Authority in Mathematics and Education

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ABSTRACT: This paper establishes two linked problems of necessity and authority in mathematics. First, in what way are the ideas, methods and results of mathematics taught in school necessary? Second, on what basis is the metaphysical necessity of mathematical solutions, results, and truths asserted, and is this justified? These primary problems raise a suite of further questions: How are the authority of the teacher and the authority of mathematics related? How does the necessity of mathematics translate into necessity in the mathematics classroom? Mathematical necessity is encountered in schools in the form of required tasks and the expression of social and epistemic authority by teachers, including their attitudes about mathematical processes. Mathematical necessity is both socially imposed and taught within schools and colleges and is an aspect that sustains the culture of mathematics. The pedagogical imposition thereof contributes to the discourse of metaphysical necessity in mathematics communicated to the wider public, as well to the formation of future mathematicians. In considering this problem space, the claims for the metaphysical necessity of both logic and mathematics are considered, critiqued, and rejected. It is argued that the necessity and authority of mathematics is grounded not in mathematics itself, but instead in well-entrenched social practices, and ultimately rests on customs, norms and rules. In short, mathematical necessity is normative, not absolute or metaphysical.

KEYWORDS: *metaphysical necessity; custom; rule-following; compulsion; teacher authority; mathematical authority; logic*

Introduction

This paper examines two problems with complex questions that link the ideas of necessity and authority in mathematics education and in mathematics more broadly. First, it asks, in what way are the ideas, methods and results taught in school mathematics *necessary*? This main question evokes several others: How does this relate to the authority of the teacher in the classroom? In what way is necessity in the mathematics classroom based on the authority of mathematics?

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Second, concerning mathematics, the juxtaposition of these ideas prompts another major question: what is the basis for the claim that the necessity of mathematical truths and results is metaphysical? As with the above, secondary questions emerge: Is its necessity forced upon us by some transcendent superhuman compulsion? What authority requires, guarantees or compels this necessity, as well as that found in logic?

Overall, this paper tackles the problem of necessity in mathematics education. It concerns the dispositions and practices of mathematicians and teachers and students of mathematics. I argue below that the development of these dispositions is through mathematical enculturation, within the social practices of mathematics from pre-school to university. It is from this social basis that necessity is derived—not from properties of mathematics itself. The authoritative element of this enculturation process is subjection to rules, conventions, orders and instructions where mathematicians reproduce necessity for other mathematicians. The underlying necessity of mathematics, it is supposed, must be obeyed and operates at three levels during engagement with mathematical activities. As I explore them, these include: (1) instructional orders at the social, interpersonal level, (2) necessity as inscribed within all mathematical texts including tasks, and (3) tacit and explicit rules and conventions of mathematics that delimit the permitted actions and textual transformations. At all levels these aspects of mathematical necessity command the assent of the reader or writer or teacher or student of mathematics.

Looking at the problems in this way links the teacher's authority and the necessity of mathematics with the culture of mathematics itself. Overall, my argument is that humanly derived, socially shared and essentially *normative* rules and laws underpin the authority of the teacher and necessity within mathematics. This runs counter to traditional views of mathematical necessity, which is construed as being grounded in the metaphysics of mathematical processes. Instead of a metaphysical underpinning I argue that necessity in mathematics is a well-disguised normativity. Furthermore, that uncovering this disguise may lead to mathematics education that is more humane, and ultimately more equitable and just. My claim is that mathematics is not metaphysically necessary, not some perfectly smooth wall in a mysterious space that students must climb, just because it is there. Instead, my claim is that mathematics is a body of humanly regulated techniques ultimately chosen for their utility (and sometimes for their beauty).² Student mastery of these tools will empower them. Understanding this should make mathematics more accessible to all.

Necessity and Authority in Mathematics Education

The problems of necessity and authority in mathematics education are different from those of logic and mathematics. To examine these problems, I divide my account into three sections. Initially, I consider the philosophy of authority in education to clarify the focus and purpose of this inquiry. Then I address two substantive issues. First, there are the general issues of necessity, compulsion and authority that affect the pre-school and school-aged children who engage with social processes of learning in schools. Second, I consider the mathematics-specific issues concerning of necessity and authority within the teaching and learning in mathematics.

Problems of Authority in Education

A central issue in the philosophy of education concerns the authority of the teacher. From Plato (2000), via Dewey (1903) to the present day there have been extended debates over the foundation and justification of the teacher's authority to order the lives and thought processes of their students. This in turn, relates to the problems of individual freedom and of the authority of

² The utility of mathematics is both external, a means of solving real world and scientific problems, as well as internal, as a means of solving mathematical problems and unifying the discipline, and hence a source of beauty.

the state and its institutions to control and restrict the individual. Like many philosophers one of Dewey's concerns is to legitimize authority in education. He rejects any metaphysical principles as the authoritative basis with which to legitimate authority (Dewey, 1938/1991). While accepting that schoolchildren must conform to the rules and authority, Dewey (1903) emphasises the importance of maintaining democratic ideals and institutions (e.g., sharing, justice, ethics) within school, even with very young children. However, his main concern is with how teachers share power among themselves in the decision making of the school, including curriculum and pedagogy, rather than how teachers share power with children.

Undergirding the ideas of justifications of power is the idea of authority. Metz (1978) proposes the following definition of authority: "Authority is distinguished... by the superordinate's *right* to command and subordinate's *duty* to obey" (p. 26).³ Thus an important philosophical question for education concerns the basis for the teacher's *right* to command and what underpins the student's *duty* to obey the teacher. According to Pace and Hemmings (2007) the research literature on authority acknowledges that while it is a fundamental component of classroom life, it remains a poorly understood area. Theoretical accounts often neglect empirical realities while empirical studies often lack explicit attention to authority. In the specialist mathematics education literature, little attention has been given to authority beyond discussions about democracy and the transfer of power to learners (Fried, 2020). Within mathematics education the subject of authority has added importance because of the great authority attributed to mathematics, including the necessity accorded to mathematical procedures and results (Amit & Fried, 2005).

In the defined problem space, my main concern is to examine how power and authority successfully communicate necessity within formal schooling, and how necessity is taught as a fundamental building block of mathematics and its learning. Most students learn to comply, more or less, with social authority and to accept necessity within the disciplinary demands of mathematics. When mathematical authority succeeds, necessity is inscribed into their subjectivity. The aim here is to be descriptive: to acknowledge the underlying power relations that exist, albeit in outline, and to consider their effects (Arendt, 1958).

My arguments apply in principle to the general prevailing conditions of standard schooling as they *are*, not how they *might be* or *should be*, according to some set of values or point of view. I take it for granted that within the context of schooling the teacher is authorised, given the right of command, and contractually obliged to exercise this right. Likewise, students are, in principle, obligated to obey. There are strict limits to these duties, and I will subsequently and briefly consider, such as when students refuse to obey.

This paper does not question the right of command of teachers, nor the justification of authority. The aim is not to challenge this, or to argue that some system of authority relations is the best for schooling. These are prescriptive and justificatory issues, and although vitally important, are not what is addressed in this paper, although they are critically addressed elsewhere (see, e.g., Ernest, forthcoming). In adopting a descriptive perspective, I am simply analysing the relations as found in schooling, not endorsing them. I must analyse power within the standard prevailing conditions of Western schooling in order to understand how necessity is antecedent to and permeates school mathematics at all levels. Elsewhere I have critiqued standard schooling from ideological, epistemological, pedagogical, social justice (Ernest, 1991; Ernest et al., 2016) and ethical perspectives (Ernest, 2018b). I have suggested ways of changing school power relations to shift some of the power to learners (Ernest, 2002, forthcoming). Thus, I am aware of the important

³ This definition focusses on authority as personal command but leaves out the epistemic authority of a discipline such as mathematics (Fried, 2020).

problems of ethics and social justice inevitably associated with power and authority in the classroom.

However, here I just wish to explore power as it operates in schooling, and in particular, in mathematics education. This brings me closer to the concerns of Jackson (1968) who showed how the hidden curriculum works, with its rules, routines, and regulations, how it comprises implicit ways that authority and necessity are established in schools. My mission is first, to reveal the foundations of authority and necessity, as in this paper, later to critique these dimensions from an ethical perspective, as in Ernest (forthcoming). I am also closer in my concerns to poststructuralists drawing from the work of Foucault (1976, 1980) who shows how students are socialized into hierarchies of normalization by teachers who use techniques of discipline, surveillance, and regulation that “penetrate into the smallest details of everyday life” (Hall, 2002, p. 89).

My principal concern is with how the socialisation into schooling and enculturation into school mathematics creates an inscribed mathematical subjectivity in learners who internalise the regimes of necessity in schooling (Llewellyn, 2018). Such regimes include recruitment into both the power relations of schooling, and also the ideology of necessity that permeates mathematics at all levels, before, throughout and after school, and underpins the culture of mathematical practice. To this end my account is descriptive rather than prescriptive or evaluative.

The Pre-School Child and the Schoolchild: A Descriptive Perspective

From birth to school age the young child is normally in a caring and nurturing environment under the guardianship and authority of its parent(s) or carers. During this time there is an emphatic and clear power imbalance, with the infant or child wholly or partly helpless, generally submitting to the caring and demands of the parents or carers. Babies and children live within social situations in which they are taught various routines concerning feeding, body waste elimination, sitting, standing and walking, play, talking, self-dressing, attending to and obeying commands. There is a very steep learning curve from the helplessness of the newborn baby to the semi-independence of the five-year-old that listens, speaks, self-feeds, self-dresses, has mastered toilet training, plays autonomously and interacts with others.

Parents and carers during this period are in authority, and control and command many of the child’s behaviours and actions. They intervene materially (providing food, proffering toys, pens, etc), verbally (giving orders or making requests) or sometimes physically and bodily to enable some functions (going to the toilet, dressing), or to limit others (stopping walking off, picking up things, or behaving in other ways deemed undesirable). Over the course of this period children learn about commands, instructions and tasks as actions they are required to undertake in achievement of a goal. Children become used to instruction and correction as they struggle to accomplish a variety of tasks, and these forms of interaction should enable them to better complete the tasks (Laupa, 1994). Children also experience praise when they conform to the orders and requests, and sanctions when they do not follow orders and obey instructions, for there are always some acts of non-compliance.⁴

Overall young children are well schooled into the nature and meaning of requests, orders, commands, and the nature and meaning of set tasks as a category of required actions. They are also familiar with conversational interactions, including instruction and correction as they work on a variety of tasks. An important part of parenting and taking care of children is inculcating them into the practice of responding to commanding conversations or language games in shared forms of life (Wittgenstein, 1953).

⁴ I acknowledge that I draw upon my experience of Western expectations and patterns of behaviour, and not all cultures are so controlling in child rearing. In addition, some are more authoritarian.

Because of my emphasis on power, authority and necessity in this paper I have not mentioned the most important factor in the parent/carer-child relationship. This is *love* for the child. Without this love the child cannot develop into a full, healthy and balanced person (Erikson, 1964). It is argued by Lewis et al. (2000) on the basis of brain studies and other research that children establish deep emotional and cognitive resonance with those around them through which they love and learn they are loved, and this forms the foundation of their affective being. Love is manifested in making eye contact, displaying interest, giving attention, providing selfless care, keeping a watchful eye on the child to meet their needs (bodily and emotional), being available, and providing overall responsiveness (Lewis et al., 2000). Love also includes playing with children and withdrawing support from them appropriately as they become more capable, within their zone of proximal development where they learn to do things independently (Vygotsky, 1978).

As their capacities and personhood are shaped through interactions with parents, other persons and the environment, children are all the while learning. Most of this learning takes place at the intuitive level through perceiving regularities in experiences. For example, as they participate in and induce patterns in the use of language, they build up growing linguistic capabilities. Unconsciously inferred patterns of language use are tested out in speech and corrected on the basis of others' responses (Batterink & Neville, 2013). Mostly children interact with more powerful adults, and many of these interactions need to be responsive, based on the child's expressed needs and desires. But children also interact with peers of comparable power and also younger children and pets who may be less dominant, less powerful.

By the time they are ready for school children are well versed in how to respond to questions, requests, orders, commands, and the undertaking of tasks and imposed activities. They are expected to have developed levels of self-control and impulse-control so that they can comply with the authority of the teacher. Ideally, they should accommodate authority through a willingness to perform activities driven by motives both intrinsic, that is, self-satisfaction, and extrinsic, stemming from the desire to please others, or to achieve an external reward. They will be used to rewards and sanctions to encourage compliance, ideally more rewards and less sanctions, and these latter in only light forms.⁵ The level of compliance and subservience reached should ideally be limited, with a respect for the child's autonomy, self-expression and needs. For better functioning children need to learn that sometimes the gratification of their own desires and needs need to be delayed for the benefit of the wider social group.

Students beginning school are already, at least in part, prepared for class discipline.⁶ They normally have a basis from home for staying in position, not interrupting, paying attention to and persisting in tasks. Few researchers, with the exception of Fried (2020), acknowledge the importance of tasks as material activities that embody power relations, regulated by the teacher's authority and disciplinary knowledge, which differs in many ways from the authority derived from the love of their parents. The discipline children learn also includes orderly behaviour, school attendance, punctuality, and so on. Students learn to access study materials and writing implements, navigate within the school, follow a timetable, take homework and bring it back as required.

Thus, during the course of a standard education, in the West and elsewhere, students are enculturated into the institution of schooling. This includes complying with a complex set of rules

⁵ This recommendation is based on the ideal of effective rearing, although it is also underpinned by ethics. Where strong sanctions and punishments are used, it is reported to result in lower levels of healthy development in children (Gershoff, 2002).

⁶ The compulsory nature of school education for all is a modern imposition, with just a few authorised exceptions (Power, 2022). I accept it without questioning its basis, as part of 'how things are', certainly throughout Europe and the Anglophone world.

concerning obedience and the respect of power. Over time the necessity of conforming to school and classroom expectations is internalised. Acquired attitudes include self-regulation, attention to the teacher, and engagement with learning tasks. The institution of schooling thus imposes an order of discipline and control on children (Foucault, 1976). Students are subjectified and disciplined to accept the compulsions of schooling and the authority of the teacher.

Not all students fully accept the necessity of schooling, comply with its demands, or submit to the authority of the teacher. Classic studies of resistance include that of Willis (1977) concerning the resistance of working-class ‘lads’ in an English high school. They refused to cooperate with and legitimize the middle-class competitive system of schooling, because it perpetuates social inequality. Ogbu (2003) investigated student resistance and a ‘low-effort syndrome’ among Black students in the USA as an oppositional response to a long history of White discrimination.

Thus, for various reasons, some psychological and social issues, a minority of students resist aspects of the power regime of schooling. Typically, this results in the expression of authority in an escalating sequence of sanctions, including, in the last resort, the use of physical force. Overall, schooling requires student compliance with its authority, and enforces its power with violence.⁷ And learning mathematics comprises a special case of the students’ confrontation with authority.

The Learning of Mathematics in School and College: A Descriptive Perspective

The stage is now set for a consideration of the compulsions, the exercise of power, and the imposition of necessity in the teaching and learning of mathematics. In the mathematics classroom at least two identifiable forms of power are at work. First there is the social power of schooling with all the aspects and dimensions considered above. Second, there is the power and necessity inscribed in the discipline of mathematics itself, which students must acknowledge, accommodate, utilise and master. Of course, the teacher straddles these two dimensions; indeed, part of their job is to weave the dimensions together seamlessly so that the necessity of mathematics becomes socially engrained. In this scenario, the teacher is both *in* authority (social controller) and *an* authority (relevant knowledge expert and determiner of correctness).

In fact, the necessities and compulsions implicated in learning mathematics begin in the home or playgroup. As well as gaining a growing mastery of spoken language, a child will most likely engage in simple number and shape games. Typically, these will include learning and using the names of simple geometric shapes and spoken number names, as well as their correct order. A growing familiarity with single digit numerals (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, etc) is also likely. Such activities will continue in early years school with the introduction of elementary operations, such as addition and use of the addition sign ‘+’. In every case correct usage is rule-based, regulated by more knowledgeable others.

The mathematics learning task is the pivotal activity in the mathematics classroom (Watson, 2007). “[T]he most important activity in mathematics classrooms is the learning task” (Boaler, 2016, p. 56). It is the unit of work imposed by the teacher on the learner through their social authority and judged as to successful completion through their epistemological authority.

The idea of task has already been introduced in the home and occurs throughout schooling. Mathematical tasks are orally or textually presented and may be enacted in a variety of media. A mathematical task begins with a mathematical representation, a multimodal text, and requires the

⁷ As indicated in the “Problems of Authority in Education” subsection, I do not advocate strong authority in education, I just describe how it is. My view is that authority should be tempered through listening to children and respecting their agency, and including elements of choice and democracy, as advocated by Dewey (1916) and others (Fried 2020). However, the expression of any educational philosophy is constrained by its location within a largely authoritarian, normally state-controlled, institution.

application of rules to transform the representation, in a series of steps, to a required end form. In a calculation this is the numerical answer (Ernest, 2008, 2018a).

Generally, a mathematical learning task has the following properties:

1. **Externally imposed.** It is an externally imposed activity directed by a person in power (e.g., teacher), representing a social institution (the school).
2. **Goal directed.** It is a purposeful activity requiring learner acceptance of the imposed goal and concerted human work, in acting so as to achieve its goal.⁸
3. **Textual activity.** It requires deliberate and focussed learner effort involving both reading and writing of mathematical texts in its performance, in order to achieve the goal.⁹
4. **Externally judged.** It is subject to the judgement of those in power as to the permissibility of the solution processes that are applied and as to the overall successful completion of the task.

Power is at work throughout a mathematical task; here I will analyse it at two levels. First, at the social level, the teacher imposes the task and requires that it be attempted by the learner. Thus, the teacher sets, monitors and controls permitted classroom activities, and keeps the students ‘on task’. This first level is most apparent in point one indicated above but is also present in the supervision of points two and three.

Second, within the task itself, power is at work through the permitted rules and transformations of the text. This is the major focus of point four but is also apparent in point three through the supervision of mathematical methods employed. For a mathematical learning task to be properly performed, the student must understand that there are accepted and permitted transformations and rule applications that are required. Thus, every student, including the most junior apprentice mathematician, must act as a conduit through which the imperatives of mathematics work. They must follow certain prescribed actions in the correct sequence.

As the mathematical learning tasks become more complex the student has choices as to which rules to apply in building steps towards the solution, but otherwise all is imperative driven. Even where there is choice, only rules that preserve the value of expressions (numerical or truth value) can be chosen. These transform one step into another that follows by necessity and leads towards the answer. Mathematics is a rule driven game, and the rules are the most important part of mathematics. As social norms and customs of the mathematics classroom dictate, these rules are necessary, and they embody mathematical necessity.¹⁰

Tasks—for example, discrete, limited computations—make up the bulk of activity in the teaching and learning of mathematics. Over their mathematics learning careers, which in Britain continues from 5 to 16 years (and beyond), students mostly work on teacher set mathematical tasks. Estimating that the average British child works on 5 to 50 such tasks per day, for 200 days each year, they will attempt as many as 10,000 to 200,000 tasks during their statutory mathematics

⁸ Gerofsky (1996) adds that tasks, especially ‘word problems’, also bring with them a set of assumptions about what to attend to and what to ignore among the available meanings.

⁹ The term text is used throughout in its broadest semiotic sense, as a constellation of signs, combining a selection of spoken, gestural, verbal, diagrammatic, alphanumeric signs and even 3-D models; comprising whatever multimodal representations are required to state and perform tasks or results. Apart from spoken utterances, most texts in the mathematics classroom, and in university mathematics, go beyond the purely alphabetic because of incorporations of some of these additional signs.

¹⁰ It is claimed that rule-based actions and activities are what also give rise to the concepts and objects of mathematics (Ernest, 2023b; Sfard, 1994).

education.¹¹ All this experience, including the textual imperatives within student performance of mathematics and the numerous teacher-initiated corrections, reinforcing the rules, all deeply entrench mathematics with a lasting ideology of authority and power.¹²

To summarize, necessity occurs in two ways in mathematics. First there is the social, interpersonal level. In school the teacher sets the tasks and their goals. However, they may be hedged, the teacher issues orders to the children that require that they engage in the set mathematical activities or tasks. The necessity to engage with the task is an institutional and social necessity imposed by the teacher on the students, as part of their social control authority.

The remaining types of necessity are largely epistemological and are found in mathematical knowledge and processes. Necessity is implicated in the tools, methods and means of working tasks, and within mathematical texts themselves. Necessity is inscribed within the texts of the tasks, and the application of any mathematical procedures results in a unique and necessary outcome.¹³

The most common verb forms in mathematics, both in school and research texts, are imperatives requiring the reader to complete the activity (reading or writing) in prescribed ways (Ernest, 1994, 2018a; Rotman, 1993). Here the key characteristic is that the imperatives are in the text themselves. Thus, within the culture of mathematics accepted reasonings, solutions and proofs command the assent of the reader all the way to the conclusion.

Contributing to such necessity and authority are the tacit and explicit rules and conventions of mathematics that delimit the permitted actions and textual transformations. This is a part of the culture of mathematics that students and practitioners pick up and internalise as a residue of the myriad experiences in the social practices of school and college mathematics. These make up much of what is termed the knowledge of mathematics that is learned through the teaching and learning of mathematics.

As indicated above, mathematical texts are complex multimodal signs that can include speech, gestures, text, symbolism, diagrams, computer displays and so on. A task-in-action is more than a mathematical sign or text because there are additional social meanings and intensions. The task-in-action is the basic unit at work: the interactive triad of teacher-text- learner. The teacher issues commands including a text (the kernel of the task). The learner utters or inscribes a text in response (the answer). The teacher evaluates this text and reinforces or corrects it. Thus, the triad works in a cycle: teacher (utters, produces) a text (the representation of the task) the learner responds by producing a further text (the provisional answer), and then the teacher replies to this with a responsive text which may be an annotation of the submitted answer, constituting an evaluation. The cycle can be continued: learner (responds) text (corrected answer), potentially followed by a further linked or new cycle.

For the learner to engage in working a task, a selection must be made from the available mathematical tools, methods and means of working the task to advance towards the goal. Simple written mathematical tasks such as the addition $27+18$ require a specific taught procedure to be applied, such as column addition. They also require a specific answer to be obtained (45 in this

¹¹ Skovsmose (2005, pp. 11–12) estimates that there are “10,000 commandments, directed at the student over years of her life in the form of mathematical problems to solve”.

¹² Much of the mathematics education literature concerns optimal teaching approaches intended to enhance cognitive, affective, critical reasoning or social justice gains. Here my concern is purely descriptive; just accounting for teaching as a process that enables students to learn mathematics, without problematising any aspects of teaching itself.

¹³ This is one of the overarching definitional necessities of mathematics: Every permitted application of an operation or function must have exactly one, unique outcome. Any deviation from this leads to contradiction, thus threatening the stability of the whole edifice of mathematical knowledge.

case).¹⁴ Thus necessity is bound up with uniqueness. In some tasks there are multiple answers that are mathematically correct such as $3/8 + 1/8$ (answers include: $4/8$, $2/4$, $1/2$). Typically, only one is designated by the teacher as the correct answer, the one in simplest form ($1/2$).¹⁵ School mathematics typically has just one answer per task which is regarded as both necessary and unique. Necessity is bound into an ideology of uniqueness and certainty.

School mathematics tasks share a common structure. An initial text is given to the learner as a starting point. The learner must then apply transformations to this text and its derived products, generating a finite sequence of texts to arrive, when successful, at the answer. During the solution process, the transformation of one sign to the next must conform to the explicit or implicit rules of mathematical transformation. Thus, necessity links each stage to the next, as described above. For each rule or procedure employed correctly is a legitimated step transmitting necessity along the solution chain. At the macro level the final answer follows by necessity from the initial formulation. It is not that the solution process had to go the way it did, but that the truth or numerical value are necessarily transmitted forward down the solution sequence to the end (Ernest, 2018a).

The solution sequence, the sequence of steps from task representation to, and including, the answer, whether a calculation, problem solution, proof or application, is the major focus for negotiation and correction between learner and teacher, both during production and after task completion.¹⁶ This conversational process of negotiation and correction is the vital element in the teaching/learning process as it shapes the learner understanding of correct rule applications and their limits. The extended apprenticeship working mathematical tasks, with expert guidance and feedback, represents an enculturation into the social practice of mathematics. By the end of secondary school mathematics students will have been indoctrinated into a view of mathematics based on necessity, certainty and the expectation of unique answers. Throughout this process students will generally come to regard and accept the teacher as an epistemic authority of mathematics. The teacher becomes the classroom determiner of correctness and incorrectness, as well as simplicity (elegance), certainty and uniqueness, and represents the authority of mathematics itself. The students will have learnt that mathematics rests on necessity; necessity to perform tasks, necessity to follow the mathematical norms, rules and procedures to achieve correctness, necessity to obtain the unique answer that mathematical tasks normally require.

The Discourse of Mathematics and the Construction of the Learner

I have stressed the role of text in the reading and writing of mathematics in school. However, more widely, there is the discourse of mathematics which surrounds and constitutes learners, teachers and mathematicians via interpersonal interactions. This mathematical discourse is powerful shaper of thought and identity (Morgan, 2016). In Ernest (forthcoming) I show how the discourse of mathematics shapes classroom practices and communicates beliefs, values, ideals and ideologies, often held unconsciously by individuals and groups.

This discourse of mathematics with its ideological content is not something you, I, or students in school can chose to take or leave—the option is simply not given nor available. The ideology of mathematics has already constituted teachers and students as precisely subordinate subjects.

¹⁴ This addition could also be presented orally as a mental task, in which case it would draw on different methods, but still based on rules including symmetry, associativity, decomposition/recomposition based on distributivity, and addition facts.

¹⁵ The question arises as to whether the criterion of beauty is what underpins the requirement for the simplest answer. My view is that the simplest form is also the most useful and efficient form for subsequent mathematical work. Furthermore, this is within the context of the uniqueness ideology imposed on mathematics, which desires and requires a single, easily identified and unique answer to any task.

¹⁶ In the minimal case the solution is just a simple unadorned answer.

Foucault (1982) developed these insights arguing that over a comparatively short period of time, modern schooling has brought countless individuals and diverse populations to accept and tolerate steadily increasing degrees of subjection through increasingly granular means of control.

Applications of Foucault's ideas have stressed how discourses operate as 'regimes of truth'¹⁷ that normalise perceptions of the nature of mathematics (Walkerdine, 1988) and constructions of the able child in school mathematics (Llewellyn, 2018; Walkerdine, 1998). The discourses permeating the practices of mathematics and schooling are not only the bearers of the ideologies within them. The discourses also recruit and position individuals within the discursive practices. Such positioning is effected by the myriad of interactions concerning their own performances and the norms of mathematical success and ability.¹⁸ These norms are internalised and so is students' own positioning with regard to them, as well as their mathematical identities, through the numerous relevant interactions with teachers, parents, peers and others.

Ciaccio (2004) reports the estimate that students are subjected to fifteen thousand negative statements during twelve years of schooling. As Lerman (2001, p. 99) puts it "given the age range covered by compulsory schooling, participants' identities are at their most formative, and children are particularly vulnerable to the regulating effects of social practices". For those regarded as 'low attainers' in mathematics their labelling is inscribed within them, becoming part of their mathematical identities. Within the discourse of mathematics there is powerful ideological strand concerning mathematical ability as something you have or don't have (Boylan & Povey, 2009). This idea is promulgated as a regime of truth, so that as well as accepting this as a true description of reality, individuals are themselves (and by their own selves) positioned within it as able/not able mathematically (Shaw, 2009). McLeish (1991, p. 87) calls this the 'binary assumption' about mathematical ability. As I point out in Ernest (forthcoming) this ability labelling, having been internalised, becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy, further sustaining and reinforcing the regime of truth.

Even for the most successful of mathematics students, the positioning and subjectivities constructed through the discourse of mathematics creates their mathematical powers. It shapes their identities as performers of mathematics and followers of the rules, restrictions and necessary injunctions of mathematical texts.

One of Foucault's great contributions is thus to reconceptualise 'power' in a way that separates it from the mechanical force model, so beloved of physics. Instead, power is manifest in the myriad of interactions between people, it is embodied in the discourses and 'regimes of truth' that express the norms and boundaries of thought and the possibilities of action. Power is manifested in the activities and performances of individuals whose identities have been thus shaped, and who themselves act as agents bearing and promulgating the discourse of mathematics, with its foregrounding of authority, necessity and control (Foucault, 1982). The student and future mathematician is shaped through a process of subjectification which involves simultaneous mastery of mathematical skills and submission to the authority of the teacher and the imperatives of mathematics (Davies, 2006).

Becoming a Mathematician

Persons going on to use mathematics in their careers, or going on to be professional mathematicians, have an extended apprenticeship. They work with abstract and complex

¹⁷ A regime of truth is a discourse that holds certain things to be 'truths' and is linked to systems of power which desire it, produce it, and sustain it (Foucault, 1976).

¹⁸ Such norms have traditionally favoured middle-class males and have been a major obstacle to the recognition of the mathematical ability of girls and women, even when manifested in superior performance in mathematics (Walkerdine, 1988, 1998).

mathematical topics, rules, and tasks over the years of college. In this extended engagement, mathematical rules become automatic, unconscious and identified with the nature of mathematical objects. Imperatives become inscribed in mathematical objects and are seen as implicitly within them, rather than as the deontic (normative) rules that regulate their possible uses.¹⁹ This reinforces the journeyman mathematician's entry to a cultural realm of mathematical objects that have all the appearances of solid, real and enduring objects (Ernest, 2023a)—in other words, introduces them to the ideology of Platonism.

From its beginnings in school mathematics, the necessity and authority of mathematics are partly learned from reading and listening to mathematical texts. Mathematical orders and expressions of necessity are communicated both by expository textbooks and published proofs. These texts use the imperative more than any other language mood, such as the indicative (Ernest, 1998; Rotman, 1993). They also employ imperatives more than any other school discipline. Thus, the student or the apprentice mathematician, is subjected to and must follow mathematical imperatives to read, write and progress in mathematics. You cannot follow a mathematical proof unless you subject yourself to and follow the imperatives in the text. Like the tasks of school mathematics, proofs are transformed sequences of text. The transformations must be necessary and legitimate for the success of the proof, and there is a necessary logical flow from start to finish that must be followed. You, the reader, or the agentic element of your mathematical identity that participates in reading the mathematical proof (Rotman, 1997), are compelled by imperatives in your traverse from the start to the finish of the proof.²⁰

The process of mathematical enculturation includes understanding the central role of the mathematical task, including self-imposed tasks. The concept of task includes the roles of setter, performer and assessor. Throughout mathematics imperatives are at work, including within the performance of tasks and the writing of their solutions. All actions are subject to the rules, including those inscribed in texts. The role of the critic, internal or external, is to judge that these rules are followed faithfully. Although the necessity of performing tasks and making judgements as to their completion originate in the social power-relations of the classroom, once the concept of task is internalised it involves working to the standards learnt from teachers and assessors, through a myriad of interactions and corrections. These provide the basis for individual judgements as to when tasks are successfully completed, including self-chosen tasks.

While pursuing mathematical activities, mathematicians and others engage in extended work with texts, signs and symbols. These come to be understood as independent mathematical objects that embody the restrictions and rules in their possible uses. They rest on the community wide agreements as to their constitutions and operability. Constrained and regulated mathematical activities serve to confirm and reinforce the perceived independent existence of these mathematical objects. In addition, persons' identities as mathematicians are also validated by their access to the space of mathematical objects (Ernest, 2023a). However, the perception of solidity of this space and its contents is deceptive. It is the submission to, internalisation and absorption of the many rules, norms and tacit agreements through which mathematical activities and objects are constituted. Just as these institutions and practices bring forth the objects of mathematics, so

¹⁹ Below, in part 3, I justify the claim that the rules of mathematics are based on normative or deontic (that is social) necessity and not metaphysical (absolute and transcendental) necessity. Deontic imperatives are most commonly discussed in ethics, but I use the term in the context of knowledge practices because analogous imperatives and duties are at work.

²⁰ It is not that mathematical texts compel your attention and actions. But if you choose to participate in the language games of mathematical problem solving and proof you must follow the very clear, explicit and unambiguous rules in both reading and writing the texts.

too they bring forth the special powers and capabilities of the mathematician. It is submission to the deontics of mathematics that empowers a person mathematically and makes a mathematician.

However, mathematicians are not cowed into this subservience. The multiple experiences of successful pursuit of the goals of mathematical tasks have shaped, sharpened and directed the desire of the mathematician to answer the questions, solve the problems, prove new theorems. The mathematician's rule-shaped intuition suggests where actions and processes on mathematical objects can lead. This intuition has itself been constituted so that its direction is limited to the pathways and channels of necessity, including paths of possibility that lead, potentially, to final necessity. It follows the definitions, norms, regulations and rules and is led in the directions that can be justified by these mathematical rules. The enculturation of the mathematician is now complete. They have internalised the necessity of performativity in mathematical tasks, as well as the unyielding necessity of the rules and norms of mathematics.

However, this account of necessity and the mathematician is not intended to deny creativity, including the use of the imagination to investigate tentative lines of reasoning, possible rule reformulations or rule-breaking, or exploring not yet fully formulated math-worlds in thought. Like the musician who has mastered their instrument can improvise or play imaginatively, so too the mathematician who has mastered their instrument, with all its constraints and capacities, can also 'play' imaginatively.

Most mathematicians are convinced of the metaphysical necessity of mathematical truths. The five-thousand-year history of mathematics, and the twenty years plus of personal enculturation have promoted a belief in the absolute necessity and authority of mathematics. This belief is strengthened and confirmed through the many links and interdependencies within and across mathematics, as well as with its applications. Although humankind invented counting, we see the world, and beyond it the universe, as constituted numerically. Most of the scientific theories and technological artifacts which shape how we interpret, model and work on and in the world, rest on mathematics and the mathematization of the world. Thus, the conventions and what I claim below are the deontological necessities that structure mathematics are projected onto the world, shaping how we view it. In a reversal of causality, the applications of mathematics in the world, based on the mathematised perceptions of the world, are reflected back, imposing what seems to be the rigid grip of physical necessity on mathematical rules. Our perceptions are so formatted by our enculturation into the discourse of mathematics that we cannot see anything in the world without its cloak of mathematical structure, as if this exists independently, outside of our own and society's interpretations and projections.

In this discussion of the enculturation of the child, student and mathematician into the realm of the mathematically necessary I have postponed a deeper discussion of the foundations of necessity. In the next section I analyse mathematical necessity and argue that it is deontological, based on social norms, as opposed to being a metaphysical necessity, imposed from outside of our shared realm of earthly existence. The subsequent three sections address the major ideas using simple questions designed to understand the foundations of necessity, mathematical necessity, and necessity and authority in mathematics education. Each comprises a piece to the larger argument that suggests, in short, that there is no fundamental grounding of mathematics aside from the social rules that mathematicians have themselves devised and that are reproduced by teachers and students in social relations.

What is Necessity?

Kit Fine (2005) offers an influential philosophical analysis of necessity. He proposes that "there are three main forms of necessity—the metaphysical, the natural, and the normative—and that

none of them is reducible to the others or to any other form of necessity” (p. 235). Definitionally, “Metaphysics is the study of the nature of reality beyond the physical world” (Feser, 2014, p. 1). According to Kripke (1972) things that have metaphysical necessity cannot be otherwise, as they are necessarily what they are by virtue of their own nature.

Fine (2005) elaborates his analysis as follows. Metaphysical necessity is made up of the necessary truths of logic, mathematics, and metaphysics. Natural necessity comprises the necessary connections among events in the natural world and includes science in so far as it involves necessity. Normative necessity is constituted by the necessary principles or unconditional rules of behaviour and ethics, including compulsion by warranted authority.

In arguing that the necessary truths of logic, mathematics, and metaphysics are all of the same type, Fine is already in disagreement with some scholars. Farrell (1981) argues that metaphysical necessity is weaker than logical necessity. However, I want to support Fine’s idea that the necessary truths of logic, mathematics, and metaphysics all constitute one class.

The question remains, what is the basis or foundation for metaphysical necessity?²¹ How can something beyond the reality we inhabit force or impose necessary truths upon us, truths that exceed what the world of our experience, including those that our reasoning vouchsafes as true? Where does this necessity spring from? One answer is that the necessity of necessary truths springs from the fact that they hold in all possible worlds (Fine, 2005). Unlike physical or empirical truths which need only be true in one possible world, namely the one we inhabit, necessary truths must hold in all possible worlds. Any metaphysically possible world must be in accord with, and provide a model for, any and all necessary truths. Such a possible world can be interpreted as a model for the set of sentences which it satisfies. By a model I mean a unique assignment of values to every variable and constant in the relevant language, which makes all the sentences in the set true.

However, does the interpretation of necessary truth as any sentence true in all possible worlds, and in all possible models, simplify and elucidate the concept? My view is that possible world and model theory is just a technical calculus for expressing necessity, and it raises as many questions as it answers.

Possible world theory has been studied by many logicians and employed successfully in reasoning by many philosophers including C. I. Lewis, Saul Kripke, David Lewis, Kit Fine and others. Modal logic, the formal study of necessity and possibility, is alive and well. However, many philosophers see possible-world language as just a way of talking (Kripke, 1972). Harrison (1999, p. 5) critiques possible world explanations, and claims “the only reason for thinking that there are such things is that their existence is implied by talk about necessity and possibility”. Thus, rather than providing a foundation for necessity, the idea of possible worlds itself sits on, and presupposes the given concepts of necessity and possibility.

So, the question remains, what is this metaphysical necessity that characterises and forces the truth and universal validity on the truths of logic, mathematics, and metaphysics and makes them all necessary? Wherein lies the absolute authority of mathematics? It must be some force or property from outside the actual physical world we live in since it makes such propositions metaphysically and transcendentally true. On what basis can we invoke these transcendental powers from beyond our physical universe to vouchsafe our claims?

I will consider the claims first of logic and then of mathematics to be founded on metaphysical necessity.

²¹ Note that Putnam (1962) repudiates the idea of metaphysical necessity, and Quine (1953) goes so far as to claim that no statements, including those of logic, are immune from revision, and hence are not absolutely (nor metaphysically) necessary.

Is Metaphysical Necessity the Basis for Logical Necessity?

Logic is the science, technology and art of argument. It is the field that looks for, and provides the mechanism for the establishment of truth, via reasoning and proof. There are many different presentations of deductive logic, but they normally consist of a set of axioms or basic assumptions and a set of rules of consequence or deduction, often within a formal or semi-formal language. For example, *modus ponens* is probably the best known and most widespread deductive rule in logic. It has the following form: B can be deduced from the assumptions A and $A \rightarrow B$. Here A and B are sentences, and $A \rightarrow B$ means A materially implies B . Thus, if we know that A is true and $A \rightarrow B$ is true, we can conclude that B is true, expressed here semantically in the metalanguage.²²

The question is, on what basis can logical necessity, including the rules of deduction, be regarded as metaphysical necessity? It is not enough to assert that this metaphysical necessity *just is*. What is the foundation for this claim? How could we know this necessity? In seeking justification, what forms of confirmation are possible? Metaphysical justifications will not do, for these too will need validation leading to an infinite regress of justification (Lakatos, 1962). But if the truths of logic and mathematics only have humanistic and earthbound justifications, or any other justifications outside of a metaphysical realm, then surely they cannot be metaphysical truths?

One possible answer in favour of the metaphysical necessity of *modus ponens* is that it is impossible to deny its validity without being either self-contradictory or incoherent. That is, its denial is impossible. However, there is a philosophical literature which offers counterexamples to *modus ponens* (Piller, 1996). Indeed, Mandelkern (2020) goes so far as to claim that *modus ponens* in some cases fails to preserve truth, and also fails to preserve rational full acceptance. Thus, there are arguments that it is not valid either in terms of truth or in an informational sense. Under these circumstances it cannot be claimed that to deny *modus ponens* is self-contradictory or incoherent, and so this defence of metaphysical necessity fails.

The existence of multiple logics offers a strong argument for the cultural origins of logic and counter its claims to metaphysical necessity. Aristotelian logic is over 2000 years old, but it is inadequate for most forms of reasoning and argument. Predicate logic is much more powerful and is adequate for almost all forms of reasoning, but it was not formulated until the breakthrough work of Frege (1879/1967). Furthermore, it is far from the unique and final logic. Many other more recent forms exist, including second-order logic, modal logic, fuzzy logic, quantum logic, many-valued logics, natural deduction, relevant logic, and Intuitionist logic (Haack, 1977). Priest (1987) even argues for paraconsistent logic, a form of logic that tolerates limited contradictions.

In each of these forms of logic a different form of logical necessity is developed. How can this be if there is only one true metaphysically necessary logic? But if these different forms of logical necessity are all valid and metaphysically necessary, then metaphysical necessity fails to force one unique form of logic on us. If we have a choice about which logic to use, then there can be no metaphysical necessity. The position known as logical pluralism abandons the claim that there is one true and hence metaphysically necessary logic (Beall & Restall, 2005).²³

If logic represents the patterns of reasoning within human discourse and language, then there are two possibilities. Logic might be a 'bottom up' inductive generalisation of natural language patterns of reasoning but then it is based in empirical practice. Instead, it might be a 'top down' imposition, the regulation of the possible systems of reasoning on the basis of abstract limitations. But this is a smuggling in of metaphysical necessity at a higher level. Anyway, if all such systems

²²*Modus ponens* is often employed in formal derivations (syntactically) in the uninterpreted object language. It is the rule that permits expression B to be formally derived from the strings A and $A \rightarrow B$.

²³ Multiple logics are not problematic if their domains of application do not overlap. But when they do such as classical and Intuitionistic logics, then they cannot both be metaphysically necessary, on pain of contradiction.

are constrained by what is metaphysically necessary, the result must once again be the one true and necessary logic. But then one cannot accommodate the variant or deviant logics at play as valid.

Several modern philosophers reject the metaphysical necessity of logic. For example, Quine (1953, p. 40) argues “no statement is immune to revision. Revision even of the logical law of the excluded middle has been proposed as a means of simplifying quantum mechanics”. Hilary Putnam (1962) first argues against metaphysical necessity in his paper “It Ain’t Necessarily So”. Subsequently Putnam (1994) has been “Rethinking Mathematical Necessity” and rejects his earlier Quinean view that all statements are potentially revisable. But he argues that the strongest claim one can make is that some propositions are quasi-necessary with respect to a conceptual scheme, which is still far short of metaphysical necessity.

McAllister (2022) has shown it is not possible to uniquely characterize classical logic when working within classical set theory. She shows that on every inferential level either classical logic is not unique or there exist intuitively valid inferences of that level that are not definable in modern classical set theory. Thus, the classical logician must give up uniqueness or characterizability, or preserve both but give up classical logic.

Ultimately the claim for the existence of metaphysical necessity in logic is part of metaphysics. It cannot be resolved in terms of the material universe, for it entails the irresistible force of necessity coming from outside or beyond it. Such a domain cannot be observed, cannot be investigated by material means. Pure reasoning, imagination and belief are the only tools we have, so the claims of metaphysical necessity are neither provable nor refutable.

What, then, is the Basis for Logical Necessity?

Having rejected metaphysical necessity as the basis for logical necessity, the question remains, on what basis for does logical necessity rest?

Logical reasoning is manifested in rational argument, consisting at its most rigorous in a chain of logical steps starting with given assumptions, proceeding by rule governed inference steps to its conclusion. Thus, logical reasoning has two parts, the assumptions and the logical steps. The applications of the rules of logic in inferences results in necessary deductive steps. The explicit assumptions with which the argument begins are, at best, true axioms. Thus, truth is passed, necessarily, down the chain of steps to make the conclusion true. If the axioms are necessary and true, then the conclusion will also be necessarily true.²⁴

However, not all the assumptions on which proof is based are explicit. In fact, all logical reasoning rests on implicit, hidden and taken-for-granted assumptions. Some of the hidden assumptions underlie the axioms, some found the rules of proof, and some underpin the very language of reasoning, and the use of language itself. These assumptions rest on conventions and social agreements that are embedded in our patterns of accepted language usage and the social practices within which language is employed, and which make its use meaningful. Wittgenstein (1953) calls these our language games and forms of life.

Axioms and Explicit Assumptions. The strongest case is when we take it that the axioms are true or even necessarily true. We may believe that they are self-evidently true, such as in the example of $A = A$, meaning that the sentence A is (must be) logically equivalent to itself.²⁵ Some statements are logically necessary because we accept that it could not be otherwise, such as “sentence P or sentence not- P must hold”, the law of the excluded middle. Some assumptions are

²⁴ I postpone to the next section discussion as to whether systems of logic as a whole manifest necessity and guarantee certainty.

²⁵ I exclude the possibility of contronyms where a word (such as fast) can have contradictory meanings so that Jim is fast (running) \neq Jim is fast (tied up). These can be dealt with by fixing the meanings and thus avoiding ambiguity in the words in sentence A .

not necessarily true, but both we and our fellow interlocutor accept them as an agreed starting point for a logical deduction. Evidently this last case is not one of logical necessity, for it is based only on provisional agreement by the interlocutors.

Self-evident axioms cannot claim to be logically necessary, for they rest on subjective judgements with different persons' ideas of what is self-evident potentially varying. In addition, truths that are accepted as self-evident at one point in history are not always maintained as such over time. In the educational context, self-evidence is variable for it is the outcome of a learning process and will vary by schooling as well as by student mathematical development.

The idea that some statements are logically necessary because it is accepted that it could not be otherwise also fails to confer logical necessity. For even statements as fundamental as the law of the excluded middle are challenged, for example in Intuitionist logic. To maintain the law of the excluded middle one has to refuse to challenge it and hedge it around with assumptions and safeguards that restrict it to just those cases to which we accept it applies.

Rules of Deduction. The Rules of deduction appear very self-evident, and it is hard to accept that a rule such as *modus ponens* could possibly fail. If A is true and A logically implies B , then how could it be the case that B is not true, or somewhat weaker, that we fail to have a warrant for claiming B is necessarily true? However, as I showed above, the necessity of even *modus ponens* is challenged (Mandelkern, 2020; Piller, 1996).

So, what basis do we have for claiming that that no statement, including the rules of logic, is immune to revision? Quine (1953) and early Putnam (1962) certainly claim that the remote possibility of logical revision cannot be ruled out. As long as our agreements last, the certainty of logic is preserved. But it is our agreements and not metaphysical or absolute necessity that preserves the certainty of logic.²⁶

Implicit Assumptions. Any use of language is underpinned by a complex web of hidden and implicit assumptions, and logical deduction is no exception. For example, the self-identity of objects ($a = a$) and the self-equivalence of sentences ($A \leftrightarrow A$) are true by definition, but dependent on our unspoken assumptions. When we state ' $a = a$ ' we require the object ' a ' to be constant during our repeated uses of it. We require that our statements exist in a hermetically sealed, timeless zone where ' a ' cannot change or decay. Likewise, we assume the sentence ' A ' describes a single moment or otherwise timeless state of affairs so that ' A ' cannot a short while later claim something else or have a different truth value. These assumptions seem obvious, but they are unspoken but necessary if any claims of absolute truth are to be applied to these examples.²⁷

Peirce distinguishes between tokens and types among signs (Nöth, 1995). When we assert the identity ' $a = a$ ' we are asserting that the token which is first instance of sign ' a ' in this compound identity sign and the second token of sign ' a ' are indiscernible in terms of all their properties bar one. The tokens themselves have different spatial locations but must, to accord with the unspoken conventions of language usage, be representatives of the same type. Thus, to all extents and purposes, they are identical as signs, in meaning and in import, but based on unstated conventions. The same holds for ' A ' in ' $A \leftrightarrow A$ '.

Each instance of ' a ' in ' $a = a$ ' is a distinct token, but we expect and require that they correspond to the same type and gain their identity from this. Thus, when we claim that such

²⁶ Admitting agreements also raises the possibility of disagreements. Among logicians these will either be resolved by agreement, resolved in favour of the institutionally more powerful, or more rarely result in an offshoot school of logic such as intuitionist logic, with its own tradition of agreements.

²⁷ In dialectical logic such assumptions are withdrawn and thesis ' A ' becomes the antithesis ' $\text{not-}A$ ' and they are reconciled in synthesis ' $\text{new-}A$ ', due to the inherent logical contradiction of self-development (Bakhurst, 1991).

statements are logically necessary because it could not be otherwise, we are taking for granted a set of presuppositions and assumptions that ensure it could not be otherwise. So, it is definitional (or normative) necessity rather than metaphysical necessity that provides our certainty and necessity.

In logical reasoning, there are overt assumptions like axioms and assumed rules of logic. We accept that the correct applications of the logical rules of inference provide necessary conclusions. We accept either that the overt assumptions are in themselves necessary, or we take them as hypotheses and accept that the logical derivations from them represent necessary steps in reasoning. As logic has advanced it has aimed to make more and more of the assumptions and rules overt and necessary in this way. But there is always, and there must always be, a reservoir of implicit assumptions and tacit conventions upon which logical and reasoning and its necessity rests. Such assumptions are ineliminable, just as knowledge of language cannot be made wholly explicit (Ellis, 2017). We always know more than we can tell (Polanyi, 1967).

Logic is like chess, in that where necessity is to be found, it results from the correct applications of rules in conformity with the overall ‘game’ or system. Logical axioms and rules are not intrinsically true and correct but taken as such to enable correct lines of reasoning from assumptions to be constructed and justified.²⁸

The use the term ‘game’ here, to describe a system of logic and language usage, is by no means to trivialise it, such as in recreational game play. The key concepts of Wittgenstein’s (1953) later philosophy are those of language games (systems of linguistic usage) embedded in forms of life (materially grounded social practices).²⁹ It is on this basis that he offers his treatment of logic and necessity. Like Wittgenstein, my claim is that necessity is normative, it means following the rules embedded in our language games and forms of life. The experience of the rules, norms and customs in action enables us to make and propose logical inferences and judge that they are correct. Overtly, these involve following the rules of deduction, but judgements as to the correctness of applications always rests on the tacit knowledge gained from immersion in the practice. So, the closest we can get to necessity is by following the rules of the language games, both overt and covert. As Wittgenstein (1953) makes it quite clear, on their own, some rules do not unambiguously determine the outcome of their application.

The preceding arguments, following on from the refutation of a metaphysical foundation, suggest that only a normative justification for logical necessity is possible. Normativity is not a weak basis, for it stands on the well-founded traditions and forms of life that underpin philosophical reasoning, including, as we shall see, mathematical proof and reasoning.

What is Mathematical Necessity?

My critique of the claims for the metaphysical necessity of logic have spilled over into mathematics, for it is one of the main areas in which logic is applied. Indeed, it is the main arena in which the different modern systems of logic have been developed and formulated. Fine (2005) claims that metaphysical necessity, if it exists, encompasses the necessary truths of logic, mathematics, and metaphysics. Since metaphysics depends on logic to argue its claims, this leaves the necessary truths of mathematics to be considered.

²⁸ Logic is also different from chess in that within a deductive theory there are logical connections between many assertions which mean that individual axioms, rules or truths cannot be changed without threatening the stability and consistency of the whole system. This differs from chess where we could allow a pawn to jump up to 3 squares at first, or let kings move two squares at a time without any contradictions or destabilization of the game. This is the difference between deep norms (logic and mathematics) and surface norms (chess) discussed below.

²⁹ Additionally, language games are inseparable from forms of life, as it is largely the uses of language within social activities that confers the meaning on the linguistic expressions.

The programme in the philosophy of mathematics called logicism claimed that mathematical necessity can be reduced to logical necessity. This movement spearheaded by Frege and Russell claims that the concepts of mathematics can all be defined using appropriate forms of logic. Their second claim is that all the results of mathematics can be derived from logical principles and axioms. While the first claim was successfully demonstrated through work in the foundations of mathematics, it is widely agreed that the second failed (Kline, 1980; Maddy, 1990). There are essential axioms required in mathematics, such as the infinity axiom in Zermelo-Fraenkel set theory (there exists an infinite set) and the Axiom of Choice (one can choose one element from each set in an infinite product of sets) that are not derivable from logic (Davis, 1990; MacLane, 1986). One can point to axioms of Euclidean geometry, and of many other mathematical topics that must first be assumed to develop the relevant theories.

The key point here is that to establish mathematical truths or results, one must assume certain axioms, depending on what topic one is developing. Thus, within a theory with axiom set A any derived mathematical theorem T , cannot be claimed to be a metaphysical necessity. It is not necessary for T to be true unless one has already assumed A . What one can assert is that if C is the conjunction of axioms of A necessary to derive T , then one can assert that T is derivable from C , or more formally $C \rightarrow T$ is true.³⁰

One historical response to the ineliminability of mathematical axioms as assumptions was the retreat from Logicism into If-Thenism (Ernest, 1991; Hersh, 1997). If-Thenism argues that all mathematical results T within a system with axioms A are of the form ‘if C , then T ’. But then only this conditional statement is derivable and logically necessary. This represents a severe weakening in any claim for the metaphysical necessity of mathematical results. However, beyond thus, further serious weaknesses remain.

First, there is the problem of the soundness of mathematical axiom systems. Gödel’s (1931/1967) incompleteness theorems showed that the consistency of any mathematical theory can never be proved, subject to two very reasonable provisos. First it must be a complex enough theory to express arithmetic. Second, the proof of the consistency must not be based on a yet more powerful theory (and the assumption of its consistency). Thus, mathematical theories can never be guaranteed free from contradiction, and hence cannot be claimed to be logically or metaphysically necessary.

Second, Gödel (1931/1967) demonstrated the incompleteness of complex theories (such as those incorporating arithmetic). This means there are mathematical truths that cannot be proved. Thus proof, the best tool we have for demonstrating truth, falls short. It is not adequate for delivering all mathematical truths.

Third, there is the reliability of mathematical proofs to consider. Periodically, published and accepted proofs are found to be flawed or incorrect. Thus, the whole nexus of published mathematical knowledge cannot be said to be absolutely, let alone metaphysically, necessary. In addition, proofs are judged by human scrutineers and no human activity, or its results can be elevated to flawless, absolute or metaphysical necessity. Indeed, all mathematical activity depends on ineliminable tacit knowledge, which must be assumed to be valid if one is to accept human judgements of correctness and necessity (Lakatos, 1976).

Suppose one conceded that human proofs fall short of ideal proofs that are flawless and hence, it is argued, metaphysically necessary? First of all, there remain systemic problems about the soundness of even perfect mathematical theories and proof systems, as the above points show.

³⁰ I omit a fuller discussion of the relations between material implication, and derivability in the object language and logical entailment in the metalanguage.

Second, this concession acknowledges that published human proofs are always susceptible to imperfections, flaws and errors (Gowers, 2002). But published human proofs are all we have so metaphysical necessity remains unattainable to mathematicians and mathematics.

Fourth, virtually no mathematical proofs are written out in fully formal logical form and are thus never presented in small and logically precise enough steps to be checked mechanically. Even if they could be checked mechanically we would need evidence that the programme doing the checking is absolutely beyond error (MacKenzie, 2004). This is not possible, on pain of an infinite regression of justifications. Even if proofs were published in small and logically precise steps, they would be too long for human mathematicians to be able to check them in a reasonable amount of time (Ernest, 1998).

Fifth, there is serious disagreement about which axioms and proof methods are allowable in mathematics. Intuitionists reject a number of axioms, for example, the laws of the excluded middle and of double negation. Intuitionists argue that these laws or axioms are false and thus unacceptable, for they entail assertions about existence without showing how the existents can be constructed. Just as truth does not imply provability, so classical proof of the existence of a mathematical object does not imply it there is a method of constructing it. This is unacceptable to Intuitionists.

Intuitionist logicians and constructivist mathematicians are legitimate members of the mathematics community who draw on a basis that is different and non-compatible with that of classical mathematics, in arguing which are the necessary laws and correct theorems of mathematics. But surely metaphysical necessity, if it exists, only allows for a unique set of logical rules and axioms? If it is possible to choose which axioms and rules of inference one can adopt for the same domain, then they are not forced on one by metaphysical necessity. If different persons correctly use different rules of inference which their community accepts as both valid and necessary, then surely the claims of metaphysical necessity are eroded?

As Putnam (1994, p. 262) argues, revisions in classical logic and mathematics are conceivable. "I myself have expressed sympathy for both quantum logic (which gives up the distributive law) and intuitionist logic." Thus, just as it is difficult to maintain the metaphysical necessity of logic so too it is hard to justify claims of the metaphysical necessity of mathematical axioms, theories, methods, theorems and results.

My argument is that we cannot claim mathematically necessary truths, as established by mathematical proofs are metaphysically necessary. The lack of uniqueness of axioms and rules of deduction, and the lack of absolute certainty about the proofs as well as overall deductive theories, means we cannot say that mathematical theorems and truths are forced on us by metaphysical necessity. Only once we have chosen the axioms, theories and rules of deduction can we call the results certainties. Even in such case the certainty is bounded by the limits of what is humanly achievable, which never reaches as far as absolute certainty (Lakatos, 1976).

Over 300 years ago Vico (1710/1914) had that the insight that we know the *a priori* truth of mathematics not because it is forced on us by metaphysical necessity, but because we have made it ourselves.

Such *a priori* knowledge can extend only to what the knower himself has created. It is true of mathematical knowledge precisely because men themselves have made mathematics. It is not, as Descartes supposed, discovery of an objective structure, the eternal and most general characteristics of the real world but rather invention: invention of a symbolic system which men can logically guarantee only because men have made it themselves, irrefutable only because it is a figment of man's own creative intellect. (Berlin, 1969, p. 371)

What is the Source of Necessity and Authority in Mathematics?

Mathematical proof is the best system we have for providing and delivering the truths of mathematics. We have formal, semi-formal and informal proofs in mathematics, and the best published proofs may be described as semi-formal. If one reads a simple and informal proof, such as Pythagoras' Theorem, or Euclid's proof of the infinity of primes, one is convinced by the logic and reasoning. But, to what extent is any proof metaphysically necessary? Each step follows by reasoning from the last. We are led to a conclusion through what seem to be necessary steps. Of course, we have to have learned what all the elements of language (variables, constants, use of suffices), concepts (number, prime number) and their operations (addition, multiplication, division) mean and how to use them, as well as some preliminary knowledge. We also have to be used to reading arguments and informal mathematical proofs and being convinced by them. Do these come together to point to the metaphysical necessity of the result, or have we been enculturated into reading proofs and finding this one fully convincing? Suppose someone rejects a proof. Does this mean that metaphysical necessity is only acting on some people, but does not force itself on others? But if it only carries those along who have been appropriately prepared, conditioned, enculturated, if only the believers believe, where lies the irresistible and implacable authority that imposes the universal and necessary truth on all?

So, what is the source of necessity in mathematics? The term 'source' can be interpreted in three different ways. First, as the philosophical foundation of mathematical necessity, uncovered through analysis of the logical and metaphysical categories on which it rests, and that define its nature and character. Second, there is the historical basis of necessity in mathematics, the genealogy of the layered and shifting key concepts and practices over the development of mathematics from ancient to modern times, to use the metaphor of Foucault (1976). Third, there is the personal basis of necessity in mathematics, as evidenced in participation in the practices of reading and writing mathematical proofs and the development and enrichment of these skills over time. What types of structured experiences lead to these personal developments?

Traditionally, analytic philosophy has only been concerned with the first type of source, the philosophical basis. The second source is relegated to history. The third to psychology and education and excluded from consideration as falling outside the proper concerns of philosophy. Looking to cultural phylogeny and personal ontogeny as sources of necessity is viewed as a category error.

However, I wish to argue that to regard mathematical necessity as a ready-made and irreducible category of modality, rather than a property of mathematical knowing, is itself to make a category error. Mathematical knowing is all the while in a state of becoming. To understand any reasoning about necessity is not only to be a rational subject, but also to have an extensive experience of all of the terms and concepts involved, and their meanings and interconnections. Such experience can only come from an extensive education and apprenticeship in using these terms and concepts in social practices, and through interaction with more knowledgeable others, over a significant period of time (Vygotsky, 1978).

Thus, my claim is that the primary source of necessity in mathematics is the third one, necessity is learned. That is, it emerges from a personal immersion in the practices of mathematics with growing skills of reading and writing mathematics. This experience includes the development of proof skills, with the accompanying comprehension and mastery of the concepts of necessity in mathematics. Only when mathematical necessity and its cognates are grasped in this way can they be understood and used in practice.

To this I should add that the absolute and metaphysical basis of mathematical necessity is also an ideological assumption within the discourse of mathematics. Thus, even those people who are

only partially inducted into the social practices of mathematics will learn it from this powerful and reinforcing discourse.

But in the case that it is learned, returning to the philosophical inquiry, what type of necessity is mathematical necessity? My claim is that it is normative necessity. It is deontic necessity, brought about by imperative-based training in agreement to rules and conventions resulting in conformity of practice. This obedience is manifested in the acceptance of the rules and norms where explicit, and alignment in modes of practice, where tacit. Socially imposed guidance and compulsion become adopted as self-regulation. Mathematics is constituted by social practices, including, among others, schooling, college teaching, and research practices. Within these practices participants learn what it is to do mathematics, what subject matter and problems are addressed, what rules determine the practice, how the rules are used within the community, and the evaluation criteria for judging good or correct productions within the practices. Wittgenstein (1953) makes a strong case that much of mathematics and mathematical practice is based on ‘following a rule’ where there is no explicit procedure, and this depends on how mathematicians have internalised normative practices and their directives. This is normative necessity.

In joining and participating in a social practice, such as the practice of research in mathematics, persons - mathematicians - accept, learn and apply the ‘rules of the game’. Many of the rules in play in the social practices of research in mathematics are implicit and tacit and are learned as ‘the way things are done’. Thus, learning to write proofs is a form of apprenticeship (Rogoff, 1995). It builds up from on extensive guided experience in the writing of proofs earlier in the mathematician’s education. In the social practice of research mathematics, continuing through doctoral study, such skills, with their explicit and implicit components are extended with increased demands of depth and complexity, partly based on a careful study of exemplars. Key published proofs serve as models or ‘paradigms’ for the writing of new proofs, using ‘paradigm’ in the narrowest of the senses (corresponding to exemplar) employed by Kuhn (1970). Immersion in the social practices of research mathematics leads to the internationalization and appropriation of proof practices. The implicit rules of ‘how it is done’ as evidenced in the work of experienced authors and authorities in research mathematics provide a template for the novice researcher to emulate and use. Corrections and feedback from mentors and more experienced researchers help to shape and modify proof practices and applications of norms as well as the underlying tacit rules.

Children learn natural language from immersion in social practices and activities in which language is used, supported by correction of their own attempts to use language, and then used in a modified form (Bruner, 1983). The children may learn some explicit rules of grammar, but most correct usage is learned implicitly, by following patterns manifested in speech, and correcting their own usage (Brigaglia, 2016). Likewise, fluency in the reading and writing of proofs is gained through graduated practice and experiences with written examples (Heinemann, 1974). Beyond the exemplars, the rules of proof production are manifested in their most overt form in critiques directed at the submissions made by junior research mathematicians from their supervisors, senior colleagues, referees and journal editors. Such critiques are normative, they help shape examples of submissions in ways that conform to the largely implicit rules of proof writing in the practices of research mathematics.

Mathematical Norms

There are many norms in the practice of research mathematics. These pertain to (1) interpersonal relationships within the social practice, including the acceptance of and acknowledgement of power differentials and authority, such as those manifested in gate-keeping; (2) the type and choice of problems addressed and theorems proved, both in terms of their significance and how they relate to the broader field of mathematics; (3) the nature, content and

style of the proofs, including references to other results, and the levels of explanation, proof steps and jumps in reasoning that are acceptable; (4) the rhetoric of written mathematics in the particular specialism, how papers should be structured and organised as linguistic productions (Knuth 1985); (5) the identification of correct and incorrect proof steps. None of these rules or norms of the practice in research mathematics are, or can ever be made, fully explicit. It is the concrete manifestation of these norms in both exemplars and critical feedback that shapes and regulates the nature of new published knowledge contributions. The norms of justifiability and acceptability, proxies for mathematical certainty or near-certainty, are enforced by knowledge gatekeepers (supervisors, senior mathematicians, referees and journal editors) in their judgements of submissions. The emergence of new mathematical knowledge contributions, including both formation and acceptability judgements, follows a conversational, back and forth, pattern (Ernest, 1998, 2023a).

Thus, mathematical necessity is learned as a product of norms applied over time so as to warrant specific mathematical knowledge productions as correct, true and necessary. Its definition is extensional, given by exemplars warranted as necessary, rather than intensional, given by explicit statements of definition. As an abstract category the concept of necessity can be wielded by metaphysicians as if it has a solid, if abstract, presence. In practice, it is determined by a myriad of material interactions drawing on persons' judgements and their outcomes. These are an essential part of the social construction of mathematical knowledge, drawing on human conversation (Ernest, 1998, 2023a). This human fabrication, as Vico (1710/1914) argues, is the only one we can know with certainty. It is the sole embodiment of necessity, resting as it does on our own rules, norms, language games, forms of life and lived epistemic practices. Mathematics is, as Vico suggests, a figment of man's creative intellect (Dewey, 1920).

Overall, my conclusion disagrees with Fine (2005). He claims there are three main forms of necessity and that none is reducible to the others. My argument is that metaphysical necessity does not exist in its own right, and what is claimed to be metaphysical necessity is reducible to normative necessity. Social imperatives, tacit and explicit, are much more powerful than is often acknowledged, and become so deeply entrenched in our behaviour and beliefs that we attribute the status of absolute necessity to them.³¹ Such imperatives are indelibly inscribed in cultural practices, and as such transcend any individual or small group of individuals (Loftis, 1999). But this does not make them absolute or metaphysically necessary. They just end up looking that way. Furthermore, they end up as part of an ideology that asserts that they just are that way, serving as a part of a regime of truth within mathematical discourse.

I have arrived at the conclusion that necessity, whether labelled as 'metaphysical' or otherwise, is deontological, in the sense of a socially imposed epistemic duty or compulsion, and normative (Marta Reolon, 2021). However, I want to distinguish two different levels of norms, deep and surface norms. The deep norms, found in logic and mathematics, are richly interconnected by logical inferences and dependencies, as well as conceptual definitions. These norms are deeply embedded in mathematical practice and mathematical traditions and no one of them can be changed without risk to the stability and consistency of the whole system. These are mainly the fifth type of norm identified above, the norms behind the identification of correct and incorrect steps in a proof. The contrasting surface norms include the rules of chess, elements of any ritual, style or fashion; also laws (legal injunctions), club and sports rules and even classroom rules. These may be firmly enforced in their settings, but one can change elements of them without jeopardising the whole practice. The rules of tennis and football serve as good examples. These have been

³¹ I use the term 'belief (in X)' to refer to certain dispositions to act as if 'X is the case' without intending commitment to enduring cognitive entities in the mind. For brevity I call such dispositions beliefs.

changed significantly over my lifetime to suit outside interests, but the games function as well as they ever did. However, the norms of logic and mathematics are deep norms which means that their necessity is well buttressed by practice and challenging them has far greater significance. Such norms are deeply embedded in the practices, expectations and traditions of mathematicians who strenuously act to preserve them. Thus, such notions as proof and truth, although based on norms, are largely preserved over time, although they do shift, little by little, over the course of history (Hersh, 1997; Kline, 1980; Lakatos, 1976).

Mathematical Authority

Mathematical authority comes in two forms, personal and impersonal. Throughout the process of mathematical enculturation students, including future mathematicians, meet and submit to the authority of the mathematics teacher. But gradually, as knowledge and skills are gained, students learn that there is a greater source of authority. This is the discipline of mathematics, appearing as an impersonal and absolute monolith of certainty standing behind the teacher. That image is still widespread, communicated by the discourse of mathematics, but there is growing acceptance that the foundations of mathematics are the well-grounded and enduring social practices of mathematics, also represented in mathematics education (Hersh, 1997; Tasić, 2001; Watson, 1990). Both the internal consistency and reliability of these historical practices, and the status with which mathematics is accorded in society serve to imbue it with great authority. This is not arbitrary, for buttressing this social status is the fact that mathematics is epistemologically the best-grounded subject of all human study. The authority of mathematics is earned and deserved. But to reify it, even deify it, in claiming to locate the basis of its necessity in some eternal realm outside of the world we live in, is to go too far in idealising it. Mathematics is one of the high points of human culture, and it affords a high degree of certainty and necessity, albeit constrained and circumscribed, that give it its great authority. But its ineluctability, necessity, certainty and authority rest on normative assumptions and conventions that lie hidden, deeply entrenched beneath our language games and forms of life (Wittgenstein, 1953). It is this basis, rather than metaphysical necessity that vouchsafes its authority.

Mathematical authority also relates to mathematicians. Successful, well-established mathematicians in high prestige university departments and with senior gatekeeping roles in the mathematics research community are accorded high levels of respect and have high status within the institutions of mathematics. What they offer as new knowledge and publications, as well as their judgements of others' work, published or going through the publication and gatekeeping channels, are likely to be given extra weight, because of their history and status. Consequently, they are regarded as mathematical authorities, and their application of mathematical norms are treated as exemplary. This is valuable and justifiable, because of their level of experience and track record of achievement. However, their privileged status in mathematics also has some risks associated with it. If such mathematicians take against a novel development in mathematics, as Kronecker did with regards to Cantor's theory of transfinite arithmetic (Dauben, 1979; Ernest, 2023a), they may obstruct, delay or even stifle growth within mathematics. Thus, since mathematical necessity is based on norms policed by mathematicians, there is always the possibility misapplications, or epistemic injustice (Rittberg et al., 2020). However, provided that new results and theories are available for scrutiny by the body of mathematicians, and not overlooked (Dutilh Novaes, 2020), there is a good chance (or a real hope) that any idiosyncratic applications or distortions of norms in application will be corrected.³²

³² It would be instructive to compare the publication of new results in mathematics with that of novels (fiction books). They differ in that there is more uniformity of judgement of mathematicians about what is a worthwhile new mathematical result, while judgements on novels are more subjective and are made by publishers on the basis of

Furthermore, the human (mathematicians') embodiment of the norms of mathematics in their practices and judgements is what allows the tradition of mathematics to grow and change. Although the norms are well entrenched in their practices, like all traditions, changes are brought about piecemeal, as new proofs are accepted and published, and as new mathematicians join the group of the more powerful gatekeeping mathematicians. Unlike physics, where revolutions take place (Kuhn 1970), these do not normally occur in mathematics since new theories are added to mathematics rather than replacing old ones (Gillies, 1992).

Following a Rule

If the rules of logic or mathematics were imposed on us by the irresistible and implacable hand of metaphysical necessity, then we could have no choice but to follow them. But Wittgenstein challenges this myth with his analysis of rule-following: "no course of action could be determined by a rule, because any course of action can be made out to accord with the rule" (Wittgenstein, 1953, §201a). While there are differences in interpreting this claim, a widespread reading is that there is always an underpinning set of preconceptions, assumptions and conventions that determine which of several directions we go in following a rule (Kripke, 1982; McDowell, 1984). This is true of the many implicit but underpinning rules of mathematical practice. In general, a rule of itself, in a vacuum, cannot determine a unique direction in which the application takes us. Mathematics is not made up of purely mechanical rule following. To understand rule-following we should understand it as resulting from inculcation into a custom or practice (McDowell, 1984). Therefore, it must always be the deontic and normative underpinnings of the rule, within the context of its application, rather than metaphysical necessity, which decides our actions, however well-hidden the norms might be under the tram-tracks of custom and expectation.

Conclusion

This concludes my treatment of the problems of necessity in mathematics education and mathematics. I have argued that the basis of necessity in mathematics consists in the adopted rules of mathematical theories and logical systems of proof and truth. These are not necessary in the sense of being the sole possible choice, or of excluding all other possible theories. In the global universe of discourse, alternatives exist, and they are not nor cannot be silenced or negated, for there is no metaphysical force to impose this.

Once particular mathematical and logical theories are adopted, conclusions follow by necessity. There are necessary consequences within a theory, but with all the limits and caveats that circumscribe theory choice. Thus, mathematical truths can be said to be necessary, but only in a relative sense (Carnap, 1956). Only once decisions and choices of foundations have been made, only when the conventions and grounding rules have been delimited, can the results that flow from the systems or theories be said to be necessary. But since this necessity is founded on conventions, the necessity is normative, following on from human decisions as to what constitute correct applications and correct behaviours. The authority of mathematics is thus limited and circumscribed and thus falls short of being absolute or metaphysically necessary.

In mathematics education, students are introduced to a conventional version of mathematics that starts with numbers and counting, and extends to further concepts, skills, topics and problems. Mathematical necessity is learned following the imposition of social necessity in schooling. The rules of mathematics, both explicit and implicit, are repeatedly applied in the performance of tasks,

economic not epistemic criteria. They are similar in that there are many sub-specialisms in mathematics with their own norms and acceptance criteria which offer a partial analogy with the subjectivity of taste in fiction, as do the differences among mathematicians in applying rules.

entrenching their apparent necessity. Although mathematical theories are informal at the school stage, the rule applications and directions are clearcut. The regime of practice, exemplification and correction, trial and error, frequently repeated, builds up the student's intuition as to how to proceed and which implicit rules to follow. The key element of this process is student subjection to rules, conventions, orders and instructions. These operate at three levels during engagement with mathematical activities: (1) orders at the social, interpersonal level, (2) necessity as inscribed within all mathematical texts, and (3) tacit and explicit rules and conventions within the culture and discourse of mathematics, as communicated during schooling. The net result is an indoctrination of the student into the regime of necessity within mathematics. Mathematical education, the collective practices of the teaching and learning of mathematics, has done its required work.

The norms and constraints that underpin mathematical truths are what make them necessary. This is contrary to the traditional view that mathematical truths are based in epistemic or alethic modality expressing metaphysical necessity, prediction and truth. Students and mathematicians may regard necessary truths as something that could not be otherwise. But it is social commitment to the character of the rules as necessary, based on the norms and conventions of mathematical practice, coupled with strength of mathematical proof, that imposes necessity on such truths. The deontic modality of mathematical language imposes obligations within mathematical culture that constitute necessity, both making it and effecting it. The outcome is that mathematical truths and the outcomes of mathematical processes cannot be perceived as other than necessary. They rest on deep norms that lock the theory into place within a near rigid structure, so that one part cannot be changed without spreading changes throughout the system.

If a dissident student should claim that mathematical truths or methods, because they simply rest on other persons' conventions and agreements, are therefore arbitrary, the answer remains the same. Mathematical truths and methods are not arbitrary, they are necessary within the system of mathematics and all of the social practices that depend on it. The historically contingent basis and the normative status of mathematical necessity does not weaken the authority of mathematics nor the authority of its uses in the social and physical worlds. Transgressing the laws of mathematics with a false statement will not draw down a thunderbolt from the metaphysical gods of necessity, but it will entail rejection and exclusion by the legitimate authorities of mathematics, and its domains of application such as physics and engineering.

Thus, my two big problems of necessity, the necessity of mathematical truths and results and the nature of necessity in mathematics education, encompassing necessary mathematical rules and procedures, learned within a social framework of compulsion, converge. It is the rules and conventions of mathematical culture that help to build up and to constitute both types of necessity. Likewise, the epistemic authority of the teacher and the authority of mathematics itself converge, and rest on the latter, which embodies necessity within its social practice.

This convergence in explanations justifies the present approach to these two problems of necessity. In addition, the solutions offered to them are interdependent and co-constituting. Coming to, becoming and being a mathematician depends essentially on engagement with mathematical tasks with their imposed directionality, first met in school, and based on using the acquired mathematical rules, norms and necessary procedures. It requires subjection to and acceptance of the social rules and deep norms of mathematics as if they were metaphysical necessities, despite their normative and deontic underpinnings. In this way the authority of mathematics is communicated, constructed and maintained.

Similarly, the formation and maintenance of mathematical necessity depends on human capacities to actively maintain and transmit the culture of mathematics, with its implicit and explicit

norms and rules. Its basis is deontic and normative, following on as it does, from historical and social choices. But it is disguised as metaphysical necessity, and this is enforced and reinforced institutionally within school and mathematical research practices. In this way the ideology of metaphysical necessity operates as a regime of truth (Foucault, 1976, 1980). My claim is that in its performance it fabricates and sustains the hegemony of metaphysical necessity as a reality. The outcome is that the authority of mathematics is grounded so firmly that its foundations appear to be absolute and unshakeable. Any student who challenges this will be rejected as being illogical in their thinking. At the very best they will be told that the assumption of necessity is required for the juggernaut of mathematics to roll on, and it is greatly needed for its powerful and effective applications.

Overall, the justificatory underpinnings of mathematical necessity and authority lie within the mathematical practices and the mathematicians that ground them. Their basis is deontic and normative, not metaphysical or absolute, however natural and unquestionable these appearances might be made to seem.

Lastly, it should be noted that necessity in both schools and the culture of mathematics is promulgated as absolute, objective and hence metaphysical necessity, and sustained as such in the discourse of mathematics as a regime of truth. Despite my philosophical critique of this status, mathematical necessity remains very powerful and commanding even though ultimately it rests on social norms, albeit deep norms. My critique is abstract and theoretical, and in no way, of itself, should lead to the questioning of the need for mathematics in the classroom. Outside of philosophy, it is only when the ethics of mathematics and its applications is brought into play that one might want to question its absolute authority, which I leave to another inquiry (*viz.* Ernest, forthcoming).

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

A Note on the Open Review Process: Author Perspective (by Paul Ernest, Ph.D.)

After submission this paper was subject to an open review process. The main reviewer Michael read the paper carefully and wrote to me, the author, offering a mixture of praise and criticism. The praise included an assertion that the paper offered valuable insights which would be a significant addition to the literature. The criticism mentioned a variety of areas in which the paper could be improved and one large structural recommendation. This concerned the placing of the two main sections concerning necessity and power in mathematics education, and the philosophical status and basis of necessity in mathematics. Originally, the latter came first, as it seemed to me there was a logical basis in treating mathematical necessity before power and necessity in education. Michael criticised this and argued that it read less well in this formation, and by putting the educational arguments first it better motivated the reader. I followed this suggestion, and I must admit he was right.

After making these and other recommended changes I send the revised paper to Michael again and he pointed up many detailed obscurities and infelicities in the text, and I followed almost all of these suggestions for improvement. The overall outcome is a better written and more readable paper. The only cost is that some passages read to me as if some alien hand was also at work in shaping the text. So, I should acknowledge here that the final paper is in fact the product of two persons working together, with overall, a jointly improved outcome. In the paper I discuss how feedback and correction play an essential part in the learning of mathematics and the internalisation of mathematical necessity. The corrections incorporated in this final version are far from necessary, in the strict sense. For writing academic papers does not subscribe to the very strict norms of correctness of mathematics. However, it illustrates how all human learning and production are

part of a conversational process in which the products are shaped and often improved. We all alternate between the roles of proponent and critic in any conversation and production, both social and individual.

Lastly, I would like to note how the warm and positive tone of the exchanges with Michael, and his explicit positive evaluation gave me confidence and removed any sense of threat in dealing with his criticisms and suggestions. The tone let me feel that the criticisms and proposals were simply a positive set of proposals for improving the paper. Rather than be ordered to correct my work by a faceless authority, I was invited to improve it by a warm-faced colleague. Thus, I wish the open review process on any submitting author. As is clear from the above, I am very grateful to Michael for his help and collaboration in the production of this paper, and offer him my heartfelt thanks.

A Note on the Open Review Process: Reviewer Perspective (by Michael E. Skyer, Ph.D.)

My experience in the open review process was entirely positive. I was invited to work with Paul Ernest at the behest of the editorial team at the *Journal for Theoretical and Marginal Mathematics Education (JTM-ME)*. My primary contribution was to provide feedback about education and ethics from the perspective of a mathematics “outsider;” whereas Paul analyses the dilemmas of authority and necessity in mathematics education, my research focuses on the interstice of power and pedagogy in deaf education. Paul’s original manuscript needed little—it was a well-formed project that had been pored over and revised and polished. However, from the perspective of a mathematics outsider, I found that there was a benefit to restructuring the paper in a way that led from experiences that were familiar to me (about teaching and learning generally) into the deep critiques of mathematical logics (about authority and necessity in mathematics education), rather than the reverse. In working with Paul, I learned a great deal. In this way, Paul is not only a theorist of mathematics but a great teacher of mathematics concepts as well. The open review process, I found, was a more humane and less abstracted approach to peer review. In it, I found that I was able to equally attend to the needs of the author as well as the needs of the product, which were intertwined. I agree with Paul that the final version is improved. I’d like to suggest here that the improvements are the result of Paul’s openness to our shared conversational inquiry into the problem space.

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